

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and **blue economy**

D3.3 - Transnational Access DMP templates

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Description of deliverable	Data management plans optimised for common transnational access project categories are described using templates within the OpenAIRE Argos on the Cloud framework.
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Quality Check Review

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Table of contents

● 1. Introduction	7
○ 1.1 Background	7
○ 1.2 Responsibilities and procedures for data management administration	8
● 2. Lessons learned from the Data Landscaping survey and proposed approaches	11
○ 2.1 Varied data practices	11
○ 2.2 FAIR data gaps	12
○ 2.3 Proprietary formats and standard operating procedure deficits	12
○ 2.4 Training and mentoring needs	13
○ 2.5 Summary of Actionable Steps	14
● 3. Strategy for generating AQUASERV data management plans for transnational service access	15
○ 3.1 Standard protocol definition	15
○ 3.2 Metadata consistency	15
○ 3.3 Proposal–DMP–report chain	16
○ 3.4 Adaptive templates	16
● 4. OpenAIRE Argos as a DMP framework	18
○ 4.1 OpenAIRE Argos terminology	19
○ 4.2 Argos in the Cloud - Plus subscription	19
● 5. AQUASERV DMP blueprints and templates	20
○ 5.1 How to use Argos from the administrators perspective	20
○ 5.2 How to use Argos from the perspective of a TA user completing a DMP	21
● Appendix 1. An example of an AQUASERV DMP using the custom Blueprint and including a dataset description of sequencing data using a Description Template	22

- 1. Main Info 22
- 2. Ethics 22
- 3. Dataset descriptions 23
- **Appendix 2. An example of a dataset description using the generic AQUASERV Description Template 26**
- Dataset descriptions 26

- List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AQUASERV	Research Infrastructure Services for Sustainable Aquaculture, Fisheries and the Blue Economy
ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HE	Horizon Europe
IT	Information Technology
PID	Persistent Identifier
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package

- Glossary

Name	Definition
Access Officer	The Access Officer (AO) is responsible for overseeing and coordinating the Transnational Access programme in AQUASERV
Access Manager	The contact person at the Access Provider who is responsible for communicating with the Access Provider and the applicant/TA user. There may be one or more Access Managers (AMs) per Access Provider. See also "Liaison Officer"
Access Provider	The organisation where the TA project is performed. Sometimes referred to as "Host"
Access Provider's facility	The premises and the platforms of the Access Provider where the TA project is performed. Sometimes simply referred to as "facility", "service-providing facility", "access-providing facility" or "host facility"
Beneficiary	An AQUASERV project partner that receives funding
Liaison officer	This term might sometimes be used synonymously with Access Manager

Station	The individual organisation, laboratory, or marine station that provides a TA service. One institute can have several stations, one beneficiary can have several institutes and/or beneficiaries
Service provider	The entity responsible for delivering services, maintaining infrastructure, or offering consulting and technical support
Transnational Access	Provision of access to a service (by an Access Provider) to a User or User group whose home institution is located in a country other than the country where the Access Provider is located
TA user - Transnational Access user	A researcher who gains access to a research service, facility, or infrastructure located in a different country from their home institution.

Executive Summary

This document offers an overview of the design and implementation of AQUASERV Data Management Plan templates. Designed to accommodate approximately 300–400 anticipated transnational access users, and following the insights gained from Deliverable D3.2, this implementation leverages OpenAIRE Argos¹ on the Cloud for flexible data management plan creation, and project-level procedures provided for the integration with the ARIA² project management system. The outcome is a set of thirteen data management plan templates mirroring the classification of AQUASERV service categories within ARIA, which will ensure that each submitted research project proposal is accompanied with an effective data management strategy.

Key objectives of the implementation include linking each transnational access project proposal in ARIA to a corresponding data management plan in Argos and ultimately to the report provided by the user at the end of the project. Documents will be hosted indefinitely in the Zenodo repository and assigned persistent identifiers. The data management plan templates will be revised when necessary based on user feedback collected over successive transnational access calls. By focusing on standard operating procedures, metadata consistency, and best practices in Open Science, AQUASERV aims to facilitate compliance with FAIR principles³ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) among all transnational access users and participating service providers.

- **1. Introduction**
 - **1.1 Background**

AQUASERV is a collaborative initiative that provides access to advanced research services in aquaculture, fisheries, and related marine fields funded under the HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions programme⁴. Through its 33 beneficiaries' involvement in six European Research Infrastructures (RIs), AQUASERV connects 63 service provider stations, offering Transnational Access (TA) to specialised facilities, expertise, and technologies across different host institutions.

Within the framework of transnational access service provision, data management is a critical component, ensuring that research outputs align with FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and EU Open Science mandates. To achieve this, every researcher participating in the TA

¹ EOSC Argos: <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/>

² ARIA – Access to Research Infrastructure Administration: <https://aria.aquaserv-ri.eu/submit-proposal>

³ FAIR Principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ AQUASERV Grant Proposal (Grant Agreement No. 101131121)

programme is required to develop a data management plan (DMP) – a structured document that outlines how data will be collected, stored, shared, and preserved throughout the project lifecycle.

This deliverable, D3.3 - Transnational Access DMP Templates, is part of Work Package 3, which focuses on Open Science policy, data management, and service customisation. It builds upon insights gained in Deliverable D3.2 (Data Landscaping)² and presents an optimised set of DMP templates tailored to different TA project categories. These templates have been developed within EOSC OpenAIRE Argos on the Cloud framework, ensuring alignment with Horizon Europe data management requirements. In accordance with project directives, TA users will generate DMPs in Argos, publish them directly on Zenodo⁵, and manually integrate them into the Access to Research Infrastructure Administration (ARIA) project management system by providing persistent identifiers (PIDs) in the final project report.

○ **1.2 Responsibilities and procedures for data management administration**

AQUASERV's approach to data management planning is built on clear responsibilities for both TA users and Access Providers. The DMP is not just a document but a guiding framework that ensures research data is acquired, documented, archived, and made available (or restricted where justified) in a structured and compliant manner. The successful implementation of a DMP relies on the coordinated efforts of both the researcher receiving Transnational Access and the hosting research station.

The TA user is responsible for drafting the DMP using the AQUASERV templates provided via OpenAIRE Argos; the overall administrative procedure is depicted in Figure 1. This process requires careful planning to ensure that all aspects of data collection, documentation, and sharing are well-defined. Beyond simply writing the plan, the TA user must actively ensure that data management protocols are followed throughout the project's lifecycle. This includes maintaining their own research data, implementing necessary storage and backup measures, and making datasets available in standardized, interoperable formats. The TA user is expected to facilitate data reuse by providing clear methodological descriptions, including details of the protocols followed during data collection and analysis. Where possible, all research outputs should be shared under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license, ensuring open access to data while acknowledging the original work. If open access is not feasible due to ethical or legal constraints, these limitations must be justified within the DMP.

While the TA user takes primary responsibility for managing their research data, the Access Provider station plays a crucial supporting role in ensuring data quality and compliance with standard practices.

⁵ **Zenodo Repository:** <https://zenodo.org/>

Stations must assist in data standardization by advising users on best practices for file formats, metadata structuring, and repository use. Each station is expected to provide base protocol documentation that the TA user can incorporate into their own methodological framework, ensuring alignment with established data collection practices. Additionally, since TA users often rely on specialised instruments and facilities, stations must ensure that users understand the outputs of these instruments. This includes offering explanations of data formats, calibration details, and any preprocessing steps applied. To maintain data integrity and completeness, stations must also provide users with all raw and processed files associated with their research, ensuring that no critical data is lost or omitted.

In addition to these core responsibilities, stations may also support metadata consistency by recommending standardized vocabularies and classification schemes. Where possible, they should offer guidance on best practices for depositing data into trusted repositories, selecting appropriate licensing, and complying with Open Science principles. In cases where researchers require additional support, training or advisory sessions on data management strategies may be beneficial.

By defining these roles clearly, AQUASERV ensures that every research project within the Transnational Access framework follows a structured and well-documented data management approach. The implementation of robust DMPs not only supports FAIR principles but also strengthens data security, transparency, and reproducibility across research communities.

AQUASERV

Research services for sustainable aquaculture, fisheries and blue economy

DATA MANAGEMENT FOR USERS

ACTIONS BEFORE VISIT

ACCEPTANCE EMAIL

The AQUASERV project management team sends the TA user an **email approving** their application. This email includes a link to the OpenAIRE Argos website, along with instructions on data management practices for their project

START YOUR DMP

2

Create an account on Argos and **complete the DMP** using the AQUASERV DMP Blueprint provided

2.a Template descriptions can be used for common services

2.b Protocols and methods should be submitted to the AQUASERV Protocols Community on protocols.io

DMP READY FOR REVIEW

3

When complete, inform the Project Management team that your DMP is **ready for review**

DMP REVIEWED

4

The DMP is **reviewed**, and updated if necessary, until approved

SUBMIT DMP

4.a If the DMP is considered complete, **submit** the DMP to Zenodo

AQUASERV Community
<https://zenodo.org/communities/aquaserv-ri>

ACTIONS AFTER VISIT

5

FINAL REPORT

Complete your projects final report. Make sure to include commentary on **how** the DMP was fulfilled

UPDATE DMP METHODS

Update your DMP to include any changes to methods and data collection made during the transnational access

7

ADD PIDS

The DMP is updated to include **DOIs** or **other PIDs** used to identify your published data sets

FINAL SUBMIT

The **final DMP is updated** on Zenodo (The DMP should have been submitted at step 4.a)

Be sure it is added to the AQUASERV Community
<https://zenodo.org/communities/aquaserv-ri>

8

AQUASERV DATA MANAGEMENT TEAM WILL OPERATE A HELPDESK TO ASSIST USERS

AQUASERVHELPDESK@UALG.PT

AQUASERV

<https://www.aquaserv-ri.eu>

aquaserv@ualg.pt

Funded by the European Union

Fig. 1: Information graphics for the AQUASERV data handling protocol, including the correspondence between AQUASERV project management and the TA user, as well as DMP preparation and publication. The workflow is divided into two parts: before and after the TA's visit.⁶

- **2. Lessons learned from the Data Landscaping survey and proposed approaches**

The AQUASERV D3.2 Data Landscaping report provided a detailed assessment of existing data management practices across 63 TA service provider stations. The survey responses highlighted significant variability in how institutions handle data collection, storage, documentation, and sharing, as well as gaps in training and infrastructure related to FAIR data principles. This section synthesises key findings from D3.2, outlines why these issues are problematic, and presents concrete steps that WP3 will take to address them through D3.3 and the improved DMP templates.

- **2.1 Varied data practices**

One of the primary challenges identified in D3.2 is the lack of standardised workflows for data management across service providers. Some stations follow structured protocols with clear metadata and data-sharing mechanisms, while others rely on *ad hoc* or file-based systems (e.g., spreadsheets). This inconsistency creates significant barriers to data interoperability, reproducibility, and long-term accessibility.

- **Current practices:**

Many stations store data locally on laboratory-based computers or external drives, with minimal metadata and no centralised repository. In some cases, data archiving is informal, relying on individual researchers' organisational habits rather than standardised workflows.

- **Why this is an issue:**

Without structured workflows and designated repositories, data is prone to loss, fragmentation, and inaccessibility, making it difficult for TA users and future researchers to retrieve and reuse it.

- **Alternatives and solutions:**

WP3 will work with stations to develop structured data workflows aligned with FAIR principles. The new DMP templates will include requirements for how data should be collected, documented, and stored, ensuring standardised workflows across all TA projects. Additionally, WP3 will provide

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/15120015>

guidance and best practice recommendations for stations that currently lack formalised data management systems.

- **2.2 FAIR data gaps**

The survey revealed that only 30% of respondents systematically publish their data, and fewer than half of the service providers have staff trained in FAIR data principles. Many institutions expressed uncertainty regarding how to implement FAIR principles in their data management.

- **Current practices:**

Some stations manually document metadata using spreadsheets or internal notes, while others do not systematically document metadata at all. Many institutions store data in formats that are not machine-readable or easily accessible, limiting interoperability.

- **Why this is an issue:**

Data that lacks clear metadata, standardised vocabularies, and machine-readable formats is difficult to find, integrate, and reuse. This hinders Open Science efforts and reduces research impact.

- **Alternatives and solutions:**

WP3 will enhance FAIR compliance by integrating metadata standardisation guidelines into the DMP templates. This will require TA users to document their data using standardised formats and vocabularies (e.g., MIXS⁷, WoRMS⁸, Marine Regions⁹). Furthermore, WP3 will develop training modules to improve data management literacy among service providers, helping them transition to FAIR-compliant workflows.

- **2.3 Proprietary formats and standard operating procedure deficits**

Many instruments produce specialised data formats that are not easily converted to open-access formats. Additionally, standard operating procedure (SOP) documentation is often incomplete or unpublished, making it difficult for TA users to understand and reproduce experimental procedures.

- **Current practices:**

While some stations provide basic SOPs for routine workflows, these are often not standardised, not publicly available, or insufficiently detailed. Proprietary data formats—especially from mass

⁷ **MIXS:** <https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/>

⁸ **WoRMS:** <https://marinespecies.org/>

⁹ **Marine Regions:** <https://www.marineregions.org/>

spectrometry, microscopy, and sequencing instruments—create challenges for data sharing and long-term preservation.

- **Why this is an issue:**

Without standardised, openly available SOPs, TA users must independently interpret instrument settings and procedures, leading to inconsistent data collection and reduced reproducibility.

Proprietary file formats further restrict data interoperability and often require specialised software to access, thereby limiting usability.

- **Alternatives and solutions:**

WP3 will encourage stations to publish their SOPs in open-access repositories, such as the newly created “AQUASERV Protocols Community” at protocols.io, making them accessible to all TA users. DMP templates will now require TA users to specify file formats and conversion options for proprietary data, ensuring that whenever possible, open formats are used (e.g., converting raw .raw or .nd2 files to standardised .tiff or .csv formats). Stations will also be encouraged to provide documentation on how to interpret instrument outputs.

- **2.4 Training and mentoring needs**

There is a strong demand for training on database management, metadata structuring, and FAIR data principles. Many service providers reported a lack of internal expertise in these areas, making it difficult for them to provide effective guidance to TA users.

- **Current practices:**

Some institutions rely on local IT staff for data management support, but in many cases, TA service providers lack dedicated personnel for handling research data. Training opportunities are limited, and data management is often seen as secondary to experimental work.

- **Why this is an issue:**

Without adequate training, research stations struggle to implement FAIR-compliant data management practices which reduces the overall quality and accessibility of AQUASERV datasets.

This also places additional burden on TA users who may not receive adequate guidance.

- **Alternatives and solutions:**

WP3 will introduce a self-paced online FAIR data course, available to both TA users and service providers. This course will cover data archiving, metadata structuring, database setup, and FAIR data principles. Additionally, WP3 will work with selected FAIR data champions within the AQUASERV network—institutions that are already excelling in data management—to mentor and support other service providers. An online, ticketed, helpdesk facility will be operated by WP3 for the

duration of the AQUASERV project to provide help and tuition in data management best-practices to TA users and Service Providers. The helpdesk email address is aquaservhelpdesk@ualg.pt.

- **2.5 Summary of Actionable Steps**

Issue Identified	Proposed Solution
Inconsistent Data Workflows	Develop structured DMP templates with clear workflow requirements. Provide best-practice guidance for standardising data collection and storage
Limited FAIR Compliance	Incorporate metadata standardisation into DMPs. Offer training on FAIR principles and data publishing
Proprietary Data Formats	Require TA users to document data formats and provide conversion options for proprietary formats. Encourage the use of open file formats.
Lack of Published SOPs	Encourage Service Providers to publish SOPs in protocols.io and ensure users have access to instrument documentation

Training Gaps	Develop an online FAIR data training course. Identify and support FAIR data experts within the AQUASERV network
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- **3. Strategy for generating AQUASERV data management plans for transnational service access**

A well-structured and comprehensive DMP ensures that research data generated during TA is collected, documented, and shared in a standardised and reproducible manner. The methodology outlined here establishes the key processes that guide DMP creation, ensuring alignment with FAIR principles and Open Science practices.

AQUASERV requires that DMPs be initiated shortly after a TA project is approved in ARIA and before research activities begin. At this stage, users must provide preliminary details on data collection methods, formats, and expected outputs. However, given the dynamic nature of research, the DMP is not a static document. Instead, it is designed to evolve throughout the project’s lifecycle. TA users will continuously update the DMP as new information becomes available—such as modifications to data processing workflows, emerging metadata requirements, or unforeseen ethical considerations. This iterative approach ensures that the final DMP accurately reflects the complete data management process and remains useful for long-term data stewardship.

- **3.1 Standard protocol definition**

Each TA user must specify how raw data will be collected, validated, and processed, ensuring compliance with relevant disciplinary standards and best practices. Where applicable, users should adopt established protocols or reference SOPs provided by the hosting station to maintain consistency across similar research activities.

- **3.2 Metadata consistency**

To facilitate data interoperability, each project must reference recognised vocabularies and adopt standardised file formats whenever possible. This process is enforced by the use of a custom-made AQUASERV-specific DMP “blueprint” in the Argos system which serves as the DMP template for TA users

to modify to their needs. The use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and machine-readable metadata is mandated to enhance data discovery and integration across research infrastructures.

- **3.3 Proposal–DMP–report chain**

AQUASERV establishes a structured data management workflow, ensuring that each approved TA proposal in ARIA is linked to a corresponding DMP in Argos. The linking will be made by WP3 administrators of ARIA after the TA user’s DMP is approved. This linkage creates a traceable project record that extends from the initial proposal stage to the final research report, reinforcing accountability in data management. The finalised DMP is published to Zenodo from Argos, along with associated datasets and metadata, will be referenced in the TA user’s final report, ensuring a persistent, well-documented research output.

- **3.4 Adaptive templates**

In the usual course of writing a DMP within the Argos system, any number of management descriptions of specific datasets can be added to the DMP. Recognising the diversity of TA projects and data types that will be generated, AQUASERV will establish a library of domain-specific Argos “Description Templates”, each aligned with an ARIA service category and the type of data it produces (Table 1). Each template within Argos will be labelled “AQUASERV | Service Category | <data type>” so that they are identifiable by TA users. The template library will grow organically as the project proceeds and common data types are identified and templated within the Argos system. While these templates provide a structured framework for data management, they remain flexible enough to accommodate specialised instrumentation, disciplinary variations, and site-specific constraints. As research progresses, users are encouraged to refine and expand their DMPs, ensuring that the document remains relevant to their evolving research needs.

DMP Description Templates will be aligned with the specific research needs of each of the 13 research Service Categories in AQUASERV.

Service Category	Description Templates
1. Behaviour & Welfare Monitoring	Emphasis on image and video formats, observational data storage, and ethical considerations regarding animal welfare

2. Biobanks	Extra details on sample preservation, metadata standards for biological samples, and data linkage to biobank registries
3. Chemical & Biochemical Analysis	Specification of instrumental analysis outputs, handling of proprietary file formats, and required calibration metadata
4. Culture & Rearing Facilities	Guidance on long-term monitoring datasets, environmental parameters, and species metadata
5. Disease Infection Facilities	Ethical and safety considerations for pathogen research, biosafety requirements, and restricted access datasets
6. e-Services (Bioinformatics, Datasets, Spatial Planning)	Specific requirements for data pipelines, computational workflows, and version control in software development
7. Experimental Facilities	Details on instrument settings, reproducibility, and documentation of experimental setups
8. Fieldwork, Ecosystem Access & Telemetry	GPS metadata, georeferencing requirements, and field protocol documentation, permits.
9. Food & Feed Quality & Safety	Regulatory requirements for food analysis, chemical safety, and archiving nutritional data

10. Microscopy & Imaging	Image format standards (TIFF, DICOM), metadata for magnification, exposure, and microscopy protocols
11. Molecular Biology & Omics	File format guidance for FASTQ, BAM, VCF, database deposition (e.g., GenBank, ENA, UniProt)
12. Sample Production	Standardisation of experimental outputs, data integration with processing pipelines, and sample metadata
13. Taxonomic Services	Guidelines for integrating taxonomic datasets into WoRMS, OBIS, GBIF, and use of species ontology

Table. 1 Service categories and anticipated domain-specific customisations to description templates

3.5.1 Cross-referencing persistent identifiers

Each DMP will have a DOI persistent identifier, assigned when published to Zenodo, and stored within the TA users final report. This cross-referencing ensures long-term traceability and ties the final user report to the same DMP. An example DMP generated for the purpose of this deliverable can be found here¹⁰ (Please note that this is a link to a Zenodo sandbox due to the use of the Argos test instance. Once the Description templates are finalized and the AQUASERV space on Argos becomes public, resolved links to Zenodo will be available).

- **4. OpenAIRE Argos as a DMP framework**

Argos is an open and collaborative EOSC platform available through the OpenAIRE service catalogue that guides users throughout the writing of data management plans to facilitate research data management activities. Within the Argos platform exists a Horizon Europe compliance template (blueprint), which has been used to guide the creation of an custom-made AQUASERV specific DMP blueprint that will be the template from which TA users will construct project-specific DMPs. The DMP creation and editing is

¹⁰ <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/records/190660>

assisted with step-by-step guidance from Argos to meet standards and FAIR principles, and to ensure readability and interoperability. Argos' streamlined process of DMP creation is finalised with a publication in the Zenodo repository and assignment of a DOI. The DMPs can be published in multiple formats, including the use of RDA standards for machine-human-readable DMPs. The general section of the plan in Argos includes key information regarding the research, such as its purpose, objectives, and the researchers involved, alongside more detailed documentation of research datasets, specifically titled "Descriptions," which highlight the processes followed and the methods employed in data management activities to ensure FAIR compliance. The use of the OpenAIRE Argos platform is key to ensuring data interoperability by enabling the standardisation of the data generated through the AQUASERV-funded TA projects.

- **4.1 OpenAIRE Argos terminology**

- Plan - a single Data Management plan
- Blueprint - a template for a for a Plan
- Description - a set of metadata describing a dataset
- Description Template - a template for a type of Description
- Description Types - a registry of different Description Templates (administrators only)

- **4.2 Argos in the Cloud - Plus subscription**

AQUASERV Data Management has adopted the Argos platform to facilitate DMP generation once a project is approved. The Argos in the Cloud - Plus subscription plan offers several additional capabilities compared to the free version, which will help meet AQUASERV's needs:

- Custom Blueprint and Description Template creation: enables the creation of a custom DMP blueprint tailored to AQUASERV's specific data management needs. Blueprints define the overall structure of a DMP, dividing it into sections with predefined templates. Additional blueprints can be created (to a total of three) if needed.
- Scalability: allows for the creation of up to 1,000 DMPs, each containing multiple project descriptions, ensuring sufficient capacity for AQUASERV's TA projects.
- Enhanced storage and deposition options: enables DMP storage in its internal database and allows DMPs to be deposited directly in Zenodo by default or in another external repository upon request.
- Integration capabilities: allows for the configuration of APIs to integrate with trusted external sources, such as the OpenAIRE Graph, which can retrieve metadata on researchers, grants, and repositories to pre-fill DMP descriptions. Additional integrations can be set up upon request.

- Multilingual support: allows the Argos interface to be translated into multiple languages, including English, German, Greek, Spanish, Croatian, Basque, Turkish, Slovak, Serbian, Portuguese, and Polish, improving accessibility for AQUASERV partners. (Note that all published DMPs are mandated to be written in English).
- Technical support and training: includes standard technical support and up to four hours of consultation, helping AQUASERV optimise the DMP workflow. Argos user and administration tutorials are also available through the online training platform OpenPlato.

• 5. AQUASERV DMP blueprints and templates

The AQUASERV Blueprint DMP template was adapted from the HE Blueprint but because AQUASERV primarily supports Transnational Access (TA) projects—which are much smaller in scope—the level of detail required in the HE blueprint is unnecessarily extensive. Many questions included in the full HE template are not relevant to AQUASERV TA users, making it an impractical requirement for routine data management. To address this the AQUASERV blueprint is a simplified version of the HE blueprint that removes non-essential questions while ensuring alignment with the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. The new version remains structured, concise, and practical, enabling TA users to efficiently document their data management practices without excessive administrative burden.

The complete DMP template (blueprint plus description templates) provided in Appendix 1 conforms to the newly created AQUASERV DMP Blueprint. This plan, including the AQUASERV blueprint and the AQUASERV genomics description template, was automatically exported to Zenodo¹¹ (again a link to Zenodo’s sandbox is currently available only).

○ 5.1 How to use Argos from the administrators perspective

- 1) Create one “BLUEPRINT” that acts as a template for all the AQUASERV TA project DMPs. Let’s call this the “AQUASERV DMP BLUEPRINT”. The ADB contains sections for all the metadata required common for all DMPs - e.g. title, name, organisation, ethics, etc. Included is a section called “Dataset Descriptions” where the details of each dataset in the DMP are going to be added by the person filling out the DMP.
- 2) Create “DESCRIPTION TEMPLATES” for each dataset type that is commonly used in AQUASERV, e.g. Genomics, Liquid Chromatography, Light Microscopy etc.

¹¹ <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/records/188048>

- **5.2 How to use Argos from the perspective of a TA user completing a DMP**

- 1) The user makes an account on Argos
- 2) The user selects “Start new Plan” (Plan here means DMP), and then selects the “AQUASERV DMP BLUEPRINT” from the list, and clicks “Proceed with this Blueprint”. This brings up the new DMP and the user answers the question in each section.
- 3) The user chooses to add one, or a set, of “Dataset Description” templates to the DMP. In the section “Dataset Descriptions” the user is presented with a list of “DESCRIPTION TEMPLATES” and the user selects the best one, or many, templates they need to describe the dataset, or datasets, they are going to describe. The user then clicks “Save” to add the templates to the DMP.
- 4) In the “Datasets Description” section of the left hand menu, is now a button labelled “+ Add Description”. The user then adds a “Dataset Description” but selecting the template that describes the dataset from the drop-down menu, then fills out the sections of the template.
- 5) The user repeats the process in 4) for each dataset that is included in the DMP.
- 6) Once complete, save the DMP

- **Appendix 1. An example of an AQUASERV DMP using the custom Blueprint and including a dataset description of sequencing data using a Description Template**

AQUASERV blueprint v4 Plan (example answers in blue)

Version 1

Description

user's answer

Funder

Grant

Researchers

John Smith (0000-0000-0000-0000)

Organizations

University of AAA

- **1. Main Info**

Title of Plan: AQUASERV blueprint v4 Plan

Description:

user's answer

Researchers:

John Smith (0000-0000-0000-0000)

Organizations:

University of AAA

Contact: John Smith (jsmith@aaaa.bb)

Access: Public

- **2. Ethics**

Introduction:

[user's answer](#)

Descriptions

Horizon Europe - Ethics

[user's answer](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe - Ethics](#)

Type: [Ethics](#)

1. Ethics

1.1 Ethics

1.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

[Yes](#)

[user's answer](#)

1.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

[Yes](#)

[user's answer](#)

- **3. Dataset descriptions**

Introduction:

[user's answer](#)

Descriptions

AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing

Template: [AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 dataset type

1.1.1 Please specify the dataset type

[user's answer](#)

2 Your research data

2.1 Sequencing machine details

2.1.1 Sequencing chemistry / kits used

[user's answer](#)

2.2 General type of data

2.2.1 additional information about your dataset

[user's answer](#)

2.3 Type of data (format)

2.3.1 Data format

[user's answer](#)

2.4 Documentation and data quality

2.4.1 How will the data be documented and described/analysed? Please specify which type of documentation record are you planning to use (e.g. paper or electronic lab book, online resource) and which software are you planning to analyse your data with

[user's answer](#)

2.5 Storage and Backup

2.5.1 Do you use any intermediate storage devices? Please describe your backup plan.

[user's answer](#)

2.6 Accessibility and long-term storage

2.6.1 Long term data storage - database

[user's answer](#)

2.6.2 Accession number

[user's answer](#)

2.7 Your metadata

2.7.1 Metadata format

[user's answer](#)

2.7.2 How is your metadata connected to the research data

[user's answer](#)

2.7.3 Metadata storage

[user's answer](#)

3 Licence/embargo

3.1 Licence

3.1.1 Under what license will you publish your research data?

[user's answer](#)

3.2 Embargo on data release

3.2.1 Embargo details

[user's answer](#)

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- **Appendix 2. An example of a dataset description using the generic AQUASERV Description Template**

- **Dataset descriptions**

Introduction:

Descriptions

AQUASERV | all categories | generic template

Template: [AQUASERV | all categories | generic template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

[user's answer](#)

1.1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

[user's answer](#)

1.1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project

[user's answer](#)

1.1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

[user's answer](#)

1.1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

[user's answer](#)

1.1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

[user's answer](#)

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

[user's answer](#)

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

[user's answer](#)

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

[user's answer](#)

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

[user's answer](#)

2.2 Making data accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

[user's answer](#)

2.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

[user's answer](#)

2.2.1.3 Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

[user's answer](#)

2.2.2 Data

2.2.2.1 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

[user's answer](#)

2.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

user's answer

2.2.2.3 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

user's answer

2.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

user's answer

2.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

user's answer

2.2.2.6 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

user's answer

2.2.3 Metadata

2.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes

2.2.3.2 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

user's answer

2.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

user's answer

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

user's answer

2.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

user's answer

2.3.3 Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

user's answer

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

user's answer

2.4.2 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

user's answer

2.4.3 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

user's answer

2.4.4 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

user's answer

2.4.5 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

user's answer

3 Data security

3.1 Data security

3.1.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

user's answer

3.1.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

[user's answer](#)

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

[user's answer](#)

4.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

[user's answer](#)

4.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

[user's answer](#)

4.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

[user's answer](#)

4.2 Making other research outputs accessible

4.2.1 Repository

4.2.1.1 Will the other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

[user's answer](#)

4.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your other research outputs will be deposited?

[user's answer](#)

4.2.1.3 Does the repository ensure that the other research outputs is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2 Other research outputs

4.2.2.1 Will all other research outputs be made openly available? If certain research outputs cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their research outputs closed if opening their research outputs goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research outputs should be made available as soon as possible.

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2.3 Will the other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the other research outputs, both during and after the end of the project?

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the other research outputs be ascertained

[user's answer](#)

4.2.2.6 Is there a need for an other research output access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive other research output)

[user's answer](#)

4.2.3 Metadata

4.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the other research outputs?

[Yes](#)

4.2.3.2 How long will the other research outputs remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after other research outputs is no longer available?

[user's answer](#)

4.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the other research outputs be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

user's answer

4.3 Making other research outputs interoperable

4.3.1 What other research outputs and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your other research outputs interoperable to allow other research outputs exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

user's answer

4.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

user's answer

4.3.3 Will your other research outputs include qualified references to other research outputs (e.g. other research outputs from your project, or other research outputs from previous research)?

user's answer

4.4 Increase other research outputs re-use

4.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate other research outputs analysis and facilitate other research outputs re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, research outputs cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

user's answer

4.4.2 Will your other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your other research outputs be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

user's answer

4.4.3 Will the other research outputs produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

user's answer

4.4.4 Will the provenance of the other research outputs be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

user's answer

4.4.5 Describe all relevant other research outputs quality assurance processes.

user's answer

4.4.6 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, research outputs security and ethical aspects.

user's answer

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Allocation of resources

5.1.1 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Direct cost

5.1.2 How will these be covered?

user's answer

5.1.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

user's answer

6 Ethics

6.1 Ethics

6.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Yes

user's answer

6.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes

user's answer

7 Other issues

7.1 Other issues

7.1.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them?)

Yes

user's answer

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